

EVIDENCE-BASED
TOXICOLOGY

EBT Cover Letter for Study Protocol Submissions

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1. Submission data

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We are pleased to submit our manuscript “‘Grey literature’ in systematic reviews and evidence syntheses on Environmental Health & Toxicology topics” to *Evidence-Based Toxicology*. We have read EBT’s [Instructions for Authors](#). We have provided below all relevant information and links as per the instructions for authors.

Our paper is a protocol for primary research

2. Basic information

We confirm that we have provided the following information:

Ref	Y/N	Item
2.1	Y	Full name, affiliations, and ORCID(s) (if available) of each author
2.2	Y	Author contributions in the form of a CRediT statement (authors may find Tenzing helpful)
2.3	Y	Structured abstract
2.4	Y	Complete funding details

2.5	Y	A fully informative disclosure of interests for all authors (template here)
2.6	Y	3rd-party data and program code are fully cited (data standard: TOP 1, level 3) Not applicable for a protocol
2.7	Y	A completed reporting checklist is in the supplemental materials (see section 4) Not applicable; currently no reporting checklist exists for survey protocols

We ask for a **CRedit statement** (item 2.2) to support making it easier to find and share information about author contributions. Authors may find the [Tenzing app](#) useful for CRedit statements (please remember to cite it, as per item 2.6). For **disclosures of interest**, we request both financial and non-financial interests to be declared; authors may find [this DOI template](#) helpful. For 3rd party data and code, we seek to comply with TOP data standards (specifically Top 1, Level 3: [click here for more information](#)).

[Authors: please add any comments or questions about the above here]

3. Data availability (data standard: TOP 2, 3, 4, level 2)

For data availability, EBT aims to comply with TOP data standards (specifically Top 2, 3, and 4, Level 2: [click here for more information](#)). In general, this means we require all data to be made maximally available, but we do not ourselves attempt to replicate a study's findings from the provided data and code.

3.1 All the data, code and research materials that a researcher will need to validate or reproduce our findings will be publicly available at this location:

No data / code / research materials is available at the protocol stage.

3.2 The following data and/or materials will be unavailable for legal or ethical reasons:

Not applicable.

4. Reporting transparency (data standard: TOP 5, level 3)

For reporting transparency, EBT aims to comply with TOP data standard 5, level 3 (modified). In essence, this means we ask submitting authors to select and complete one or more checklists that they judge to be appropriate for their research type, that support full disclosure of all key aspects of the design and analysis of their study. [Click here for more information about the relevant TOP standard](#). If no checklist is available, authors may wish to refer to the [MDAR \(Materials Design Analysis Reporting\) framework and checklist](#) or the [SPIDER framework](#) (which works for quantitative and qualitative research).

4.1 We used the **[authors: insert reporting checklist name, multiple checklists if appropriate]** checklist/s to facilitate comprehensive disclosure of key aspects of research design and data analysis.

We did not use a reporting checklist as no checklist currently exists for survey protocols. (We indicated in the protocol that the reporting of the manuscript with the survey results will be in compliance with the CHERRIES checklist).

4.2 We selected the above checklist/s because **[authors: insert reason here - or, if no checklist was used, please explain why]**.

Not applicable, see above.

5. Level of bias control in data collection

This section concerns authors' sight of data ahead of their planned study. While EBT encourages preregistration of Category 0 studies due to the advantages of preregistration when planning research, as per guidance from the Peer Community in Registered Reports Category 0 studies are not published as Registered Reports format submissions. This is because Registered Reports must be a minimum Category 1 study (see [section 2.6 of PCI-RR guidance](#)).

Ref	Preregistration Level (see guidance here)
5.1	We believe our study is best described as preregistration category Category 6

6. Index of supplemental materials

Supplemental materials contain the additional data needed for understanding and replicating the methods used in a study. Asks submitting authors to provide a numbering system, plain English title, and any necessary explanatory notes as needed, to help readers identify at a glance the content of the materials they may need to access.

We have provided the following supplemental materials alongside our Working Paper:

Number	Title	Notes (if applicable)
1	Appendix	Survey instrument (list of questions)
2	Declarations of Interest for all authors	Combined into a single file
3	Cover letter	Present document